

A guide to selecting high-performing antibodies for hnRNP H2 (UniProt ID: P55795) for use in western blot and immunoprecipitation

Vera Ruíz Moleón¹, Charles Alende^{†1}, Maryam Fotouhi^{†1}, Sara González Bolívar¹, Riham Ayoubi¹ and Carl Laflamme^{1*}, NeuroSGC/YCharOS/EDDU collaborative group and ABIF consortium

[†] Authors contributed equally

¹ Department of Neurology and Neurosurgery, Structural Genomics Consortium, The Montreal Neurological Institute, McGill University, Montreal, Quebec, Canada

* Corresponding author: carl.laflamme@mcgill.ca

Abstract

Heterogeneous nuclear ribonucleoprotein H2 (hnRNP H2) is a member of the hnRNP family, which plays key roles in RNA processing and metabolism. Here we have characterized five hnRNP H2 commercial antibodies for western blot and immunoprecipitation using a standardized experimental protocol based on comparing read-outs in knockout cell lines and isogenic parental controls. These studies are part of a larger, collaborative initiative seeking to address antibody reproducibility issues by characterizing commercially available antibodies for human proteins and publishing the results openly as a resource for the scientific community. While use of antibodies and protocols vary between laboratories, we encourage readers to use this report as a guide to select the most appropriate antibodies for their specific needs.

Keywords:

UniProt ID: P55795, *HNRNPH2*, hnRNP H2, Heterogeneous nuclear ribonucleoprotein H2, antibody characterization, antibody validation, western blot, immunoprecipitation, immunofluorescence

Introduction

The heterogeneous nuclear ribonucleoprotein (hnRNP) family comprises over 16 core members, each designated by a letter or number. Its molecular functions include binding to RNA sequences, particularly those enriched with G-rich motifs, and influencing alternative splicing by promoting or inhibiting the inclusion of specific exons. hnRNP H2 contributes to RNA stability, polyadenylation, and nuclear-cytoplasmic transport. Additionally, it participates in transcriptional regulation by interacting with other RNA-binding proteins and modulating the expression of target genes. This protein is crucial in maintaining proper gene expression and cellular function (1). Mutations in the *HNRNPH2* cause the *HNRNPH2*-Related Neurodevelopmental Disorder characterized by developmental delays and intellectual disabilities (2).

This research is part of a broader collaborative initiative in which academics, funders and commercial antibody manufacturers are working together to address antibody reproducibility issues by characterizing commercial antibodies for human proteins using standardized protocols, and openly sharing the data (3-5). Here we evaluated the performance of five commercial antibodies for hnRNP H2 for use in western blot and immunoprecipitation, enabling biochemical and cellular assessment of hnRNP H2 properties and function. The platform for antibody characterization used to carry out this study was endorsed by a committee of industry and academic representatives (6). It consists of identifying human cell lines with adequate target protein expression and the development/contribution of equivalent knockout (KO) cell lines, followed by antibody characterization procedures using most commercially available antibodies against the corresponding protein. The standardized consensus antibody characterization protocols are openly available on Protocol Exchange, a preprint server (DOI:[10.21203/rs.3.pex-2607/v1](https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.pex-2607/v1)) (7).

The authors do not engage in result analysis or offer explicit antibody recommendations. Our primary aim is to deliver top-tier data to the scientific community, grounded in Open Science principles. This empowers experts to interpret the characterization data independently, enabling them to make informed choices regarding the most suitable antibodies for their specific experimental needs. Guidelines on how to interpret antibody characterization data found in this study are featured on the YCharOS gateway (8).

Results and discussion

Our standard protocol involves comparing readouts from wild type (WT) and KO cell lines (7, 9). In the absence of commercially available KO cell lines, siRNA technology can be employed to knockdown (KD) the target gene (10, 11). To determine which cell line demonstrates high expression of hnRNP H2 and thus be appropriate for KD, we examined the DepMap (Cancer Dependency Map Portal, RRID:SCR_017655) transcriptomics database to identify cell lines that express the target at levels greater than 2.5 log₂ (transcripts per million “TPM” + 1), which we have found to be a suitable cut-off (3). DMS 53 expresses the hnRNP H2 transcript at 6.6 and was therefore identified as a suitable cell line to use here. A non-targeting control siRNA pool was used to treat DMS 53 control (ctrl) cells, while *HNRNPH2* was KD using a pool of siRNA targeting this gene.

To screen all antibodies by western blot, ctrl and *HNRNPH2* KD protein lysates were ran on SDS-PAGE, transferred onto nitrocellulose membranes, and then probed with five hnRNP H2 antibodies in parallel (Figure 1).

We then assessed the capability of all five antibodies to capture hnRNP H2 from DMS 53 protein extracts using immunoprecipitation techniques, followed by western blot analysis. For the immunoblot step, a specific hnRNP H2 antibody identified previously (refer to Figure 1) was selected. Equal amounts of the starting material (SM) and the unbound fractions (UB), as well as the whole immunoprecipitate (IP) eluates were separated by SDS-PAGE (Figure 2).

In conclusion, we have screened five hnRNP H2 commercial antibodies by western blot and immunoprecipitation by comparing the signal produced by the antibodies in human DMS 53 ctrl and *HNRNPH2* KD cells. To assist users in interpreting antibody performance, Table 3 outlines various scenarios in which antibodies may perform in all three applications (3). Several high-quality and renewable antibodies that successfully detect hnRNP H2 were identified in all applications. Researchers who wish to study hnRNP H2 in a different species are encouraged to select high-quality antibodies, based on the results of this study, and investigate the predicted species reactivity of the manufacturer before extending their research.

The underlying data for this study can be found on Zenodo, an open-access repository for which YCharOS has its own collection of antibody characterization reports.

Limitations

Inherent limitations are associated with the antibody characterization platform used in this study. Firstly, the YCharOS project focuses on renewable (recombinant and monoclonal) antibodies and does not test all commercially available hnRNP H2 antibodies. YCharOS partners provide approximately 80% of all renewable antibodies, but some top-cited polyclonal antibodies may not be available through these partners.

Secondly, the YCharOS effort employs a non-biased approach that is agnostic to the protein for which antibodies have been characterized. The aim is to provide objective data on antibody performance without preconceived notions about how antibodies should perform or the molecular weight that should be observed in western blot. As the authors are not experts in hnRNP H2 only a brief overview of the protein's function and its relevance in disease is provided. hnRNP H2 experts are invited to analyze and interpret observed banding patterns in western blots and subcellular localization in immunofluorescence.

Thirdly, YCharOS experiments are not performed in replicates primarily due to the use of multiple antibodies targeting various epitopes. Once a specific antibody is identified, it validates the protein expression of the intended target in the selected cell line, confirms the lack of protein expression in the KO cell line and supports conclusions regarding the specificity of the other antibodies. All experiments are performed using master mixes, and meticulous attention is paid to sample preparation and experimental execution. In IF, the use of two different concentrations serves to evaluate antibody specificity and can aid in assessing assay reliability. In instances where antibodies yield no signal, a repeat experiment is conducted following titration. Additionally, our independent data is performed subsequently to the antibody manufacturers internal validation process, therefore making our characterization process a repeat.

Lastly, as comprehensive and standardized procedures are respected, any conclusions remain confined to the experimental conditions and cell line used for this study. The use of a single cell type for evaluating antibody performance poses as a limitation, as factors such as target protein abundance significantly impact results (7). Additionally, the use of cancer cell lines containing gene mutations poses a potential challenge, as these mutations may be within the epitope coding sequence or other regions of the gene responsible for the intended target. Such alterations can impact the binding affinity of antibodies. This represents an inherent limitation of any approach that employs cancer cell lines.

Method

The standardized protocols used to carry out this KO cell line-based antibody characterization platform was established and approved by a collaborative group of academics, industry researchers and antibody manufacturers. The detailed materials and step-by-step protocols used to characterize antibodies in western blot and immunoprecipitation are openly available on Protocol Exchange, a preprint server (DOI:[10.21203/rs.3.pex-2607/v1](https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.pex-2607/v1)) (7). Brief descriptions of the experimental setup used to carry out this study can be found below.

Cell lines and antibodies

Cell lines used and primary antibodies tested in this study are listed in Table 1 and 2, respectively. To ensure that the cell lines and antibodies are cited properly and can be easily identified, we have included their corresponding Research Resource Identifiers, or RRID (12, 13).

To KD *HNRNPH2*, DMS 53 cells were treated with the SMARTPool ON-TARGETplus human *HNRNPH2* siRNA from Horizon Discovery, cat. number L-013245-02-0005. 5637 ctrl cells were treated with the ON-TARGETplus Non-targeting Control Pool from Horizon Discovery, cat. number. D-001810-10. Lipofectamine RNAiMAX (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 13778030) was used to transfect the siRNA following the manufacturer's protocol.

Peroxidase-conjugated goat anti-rabbit and anti-mouse antibodies are (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 65-6120 and 62-6520). Alexa-555-conjugated goat anti-rabbit and anti-mouse secondary antibodies (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number A-21429 and A-21424). Peroxidase-conjugated VeriBlot for IP Detection Reagent is from Abcam, cat. number ab131366.

Antibody screening by western blot

DMS 53 ctrl and *HNRNPH2* KD cells were collected in RIPA buffer (25mM Tris-HCl pH 7.6, 150mM NaCl, 1% NP-40, 1% sodium deoxycholate, 0.1% SDS) (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 89901) supplemented with 1x protease inhibitor cocktail mix (MilliporeSigma, cat. number P8340). Lysates were sonicated briefly and incubated 30 min on ice. Lysates were spun at $\sim 110,000 \times g$ for 15 min at 4°C and equal protein aliquots of the supernatants were analyzed by SDS-PAGE and western blot. BLUelf prestained protein ladder (GeneDireX, cat. number PM008-0500) was used.

Western blots were performed with precast midi 4-20% Tris-Glycine polyacrylamide gels (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number WXP42012BOX) ran with Tris/Glycine/SDS buffer (Bio-Rad, cat. number 1610772), loaded in Laemmli loading sample buffer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number AAJ61337AD) and transferred on nitrocellulose membranes. Proteins on the blots were visualized with Ponceau S staining (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number BP103-10) which is scanned to show together with individual western blot. Blots were blocked with 5% milk for 1 hr, and antibodies were incubated O/N at 4°C with 5% milk in TBS with 0,1% Tween 20 (TBST) (Cell Signalling Technology, cat. number 9997). Following three washes with TBST, the peroxidase conjugated secondary antibody was incubated at a dilution of $\sim 0.2 \mu\text{g/ml}$

in TBST with 5% milk for 1 hr at room temperature followed by three washes with TBST. Membranes were incubated with Pierce ECL (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 32106) prior to detection with the iBright™ CL1500 Imaging System (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number A44240).

Antibody screening by immunoprecipitation

Antibody-bead conjugates were prepared by adding 2 µg to 500 µl of Pierce IP Lysis Buffer from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 87788) in a microcentrifuge tube, together with 30 µl of Dynabeads protein A- (for rabbit antibodies) or protein G- (for mouse antibodies) (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 10002D and 10004D, respectively). Tubes were rocked for ~1 h at 4°C followed by two washes to remove unbound antibodies.

DMS 53 WT were collected in Pierce IP buffer (25 mM Tris-HCl pH 7.4, 150 mM NaCl, 1 mM EDTA, 1% NP-40 and 5% glycerol) supplemented with protease inhibitor. Lysates were rocked 30 min at 4°C and spun at 110,000 x g for 15 min at 4°C. 1 ml aliquots at 2 mg/ml of lysate were incubated with an antibody-bead conjugate for ~1 h at 4°C. The unbound fractions were collected, and beads were subsequently washed three times with 1.0 ml of IP buffer and processed for SDS-PAGE and western blot on precast midi 4-20% Tris-Glycine polyacrylamide gels. VeriBlot for IP Detection Reagent:HRP was used as a secondary detection system at a concentration of 0.1 µg/ml.

Grant information

This work was supported by a grant from the Simons Foundation Autism Research Initiative (SFARI) and from the Government of Canada through Genome Canada, Genome Quebec, and Ontario Genomics (grant no. OGI-210). RA is supported by a Mitacs fellowship.

The funders had no role in study design, data collection and analysis, decision to publish, or preparation of the manuscript.

Competing interests

For this project, the laboratory of Peter McPherson developed partnerships with high-quality antibody manufacturers and KO cell line providers. The partners provide antibodies and KO cell lines to the McPherson laboratory at no cost. These partners include: - Abcam-ABCD antibodies- ABclonal- Aviva Systems Biology -Bio Techne -Cell Signalling Technology -Developmental Studies Hybridoma Bank - GeneTex – Horizon Discovery – Proteintech – Synaptic Systems –Thermo Fisher Scientific.

Acknowledgment

We would like to thank the NeuroSGC/YCharOS/EDDU collaborative group for their important contribution to the creation of an open scientific ecosystem of antibody manufacturers and KO cell line suppliers, for the development of community-agreed protocols, and for their shared ideas, resources, and collaboration. Members of the group can be found below. We would also like to thank the Advanced BioImaging Facility (ABIF) consortium for their image analysis pipeline development and conduction (RRID:SCR_017697). Members of each group can be found below.

NeuroSGC/YCharOS/EDDU collaborative group: Thomas M. Durcan, Aled M. Edwards, Peter S. McPherson, Chetan Raina and Wolfgang Reintsch

ABIF consortium: Claire M. Brown and Joel Ryan

Thank you to the Structural Genomics Consortium, a registered charity (no. 1097737), for your support on this project. The Structural Genomics Consortium receives funding from Bayer AG, Boehringer Ingelheim, Bristol-Myers Squibb, Genentech, Genome Canada through Ontario Genomics Institute (grant no. OGI-196), the EU and EFPIA through the Innovative Medicines Initiative 2 Joint Undertaking (EUbOPEN grant no. 875510), Janssen, Merck KGaA (also known as EMD in Canada and the United States), Pfizer and Takeda.

References

1. Geuens T, Bouhy D, Timmerman V. The hnRNP family: insights into their role in health and disease. *Hum Genet.* 2016;135(8):851-67.
2. Madhok S, Bain J. HNRNPH2-Related Neurodevelopmental Disorder. In: Adam MP, Feldman J, Mirzaa GM, Pagon RA, Wallace SE, Amemiya A, editors. *GeneReviews*((R)). Seattle (WA)1993.
3. Ayoubi R, Ryan J, Biddle MS, Alshafie W, Fotouhi M, Bolivar SG, et al. Scaling of an antibody validation procedure enables quantification of antibody performance in major research applications. *Elife.* 2023;12.
4. Carter AJ, Kraemer O, Zwick M, Mueller-Fahrnow A, Arrowsmith CH, Edwards AM. Target 2035: probing the human proteome. *Drug Discov Today.* 2019;24(11):2111-5.
5. Licciardello MP, Workman P. The era of high-quality chemical probes. *RSC Medicinal Chemistry.* 2022;13(12):1446-59.
6. Ayoubi R, Ryan J, Gonzalez Bolivar S, Alende C, Ruiz Moleon V, Fotouhi M, et al. A consensus platform for antibody characterization. *Nat Protoc.* 2024.
7. Ayoubi R, Ryan J, Bolivar SG, Alende C, Moleon VR, Fotouhi M, et al. A consensus platform for antibody characterization (Version 1). *Protocol Exchange.* 2024.
8. Biddle MS, Virk HS. YCharOS open antibody characterisation data: Lessons learned and progress made F1000Research 2023. 2023;12:1344.
9. Laflamme C, McKeever PM, Kumar R, Schwartz J, Kolaoudouzan M, Chen CX, et al. Implementation of an antibody characterization procedure and application to the major ALS/FTD disease gene C9ORF72. *Elife.* 2019;8.
10. Fire A, Xu S, Montgomery MK, Kostas SA, Driver SE, Mello CC. Potent and specific genetic interference by double-stranded RNA in *Caenorhabditis elegans*. *Nature.* 1998;391(6669):806-11.
11. Dana H, Chalbatani GM, Mahmoodzadeh H, Karimloo R, Rezaiean O, Moradzadeh A, et al. Molecular Mechanisms and Biological Functions of siRNA. *Int J Biomed Sci.* 2017;13(2):48-57.
12. Bandrowski A, Pairish M, Eckmann P, Grethe J, Martone ME. The Antibody Registry: ten years of registering antibodies. *Nucleic Acids Res.* 2023;51(D1):D358-D67.
13. Bairoch A. The Cellosaurus, a Cell-Line Knowledge Resource. *J Biomol Tech.* 2018;29(2):25-38.

Table 1: Summary of the cell lines used

Institution	Catalog number	RRID (Cellosaurus)	Cell line	Genotype
ATCC	CRL-2062	CVCL_1177	DMS 53	WT

Table 2: Summary of the hnRNP H2 antibodies tested

Company	Catalog number	Lot number	RRID (Antibody Registry)	Clonality	Clone ID	Host	Concentration ($\mu\text{g}/\mu\text{L}$)	Vendors recommended applications
Abcam	ab179439**	1055577-2	AB_3099469	recombinant mono	EPR12170 (B)	rabbit	0.82	Wb, IF
Abcam	ab181171**	1070864	AB_3099468	recombinant mono	EPR12171	rabbit	0.84	Wb, IF
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA5-36290*	ZJ4492706	AB_2896812	monoclonal	1G11	mouse	1.00	Wb, IP, IF
Thermo Fisher Scientific	PA5-36254	YE3914277	AB_2553441	polyclonal	-	rabbit	1.00	Wb
Thermo Fisher Scientific	PA5-53513	YE3914203A	AB_2642497	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.10	Wb, IF

Wb=western blot; IF= immunofluorescence; IP=immunoprecipitation, **= recombinant antibody, *= monoclonal antibody

Table 3: Illustrations to assess antibody performance in all western blot and immunoprecipitation

This table has been reproduced with permission from Ayoubi et al., Elife, 2023 (3)

Figure 1: hnRNP H2 antibody screening by western blot

Figure 2: hnRNP H2 antibody screening by immunoprecipitation

FIGURE LEGENDS

Figure 1: hnRNP H2 antibody screening by western blot.

Lysates of DMS 53 ctrl and *HNRNPH2* KD were prepared, and 40 µg of protein were processed for western blot with the indicated hnRNP H2 antibodies. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are presented to show equal loading of ctrl and KD lysates and protein transfer efficiency from the acrylamide gels to the nitrocellulose membrane. Antibody dilutions were chosen according to the recommendations of the antibody supplier. Antibody dilution used: ab179439** at 1/200, ab181171** at 1/1000, MA5-36290* at 1/1000, PA5-36254 at 1/1000, PA5-53513 at 1/250. An exception was given for ab179439**, which was titrated as the signal was too weak when following the supplier's recommendations. Predicted band size: 49.2 kDa. **= recombinant antibody, *= monoclonal antibody.

Figure 2: hnRNP H2 antibody screening by immunoprecipitation.

DMS 53 lysates were prepared, and immunoprecipitation was performed using 1 mg of lysate and 2.0 µg of the indicated hnRNP H2 antibodies pre-coupled to Dynabeads protein A or protein G. Samples were washed and processed for western blot with the indicated hnRNP H2 antibody. For western blot, ab181171** was used at 1/200. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are shown. SM=3% starting material; UB=3% unbound fraction; IP=immunoprecipitate, HC= antibody heavy chain, LC= antibody light chain. **= recombinant antibody, *= monoclonal antibody.